

ISic1234

Funerary inscription for Zosima

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-12-04 - Jonathan Prag edited the file from existing editions

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

The text is only preserved in Gualtherus, who reports it himself at second hand

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina

Physical Description

No description is preserved

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

The only indication of layout is the report at second hand from Gualtherus, showing a text over six lines, with the second line apparently missing, repeated continuation of words across line-end, and possible interpuncts around the age elements

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Θεοῖς Κατα

2. [χθονίοις]

3. Ζωσίμα ἔ

4. ζησεν · ἔ

5. τη · εκ · ΟΙ

6. ΣΩΑΕ

Apparatus

Text of Gualtherus, derived 'ex schedis Alb. Piccoli'

Translation

Commentary

It seems plausible to read the EK in line 5 as the age in years, although the numeral is of ascending format in that case.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492838

EDCS 39101599

PHI 140719

Bibliography

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